

Systematic Review

Measuring Circularity of Buildings: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract: The transition to a circular economy in the construction sector is crucial for reducing environmental impacts and resource depletion. However, a lack of harmonized methodologies and standardized indicators for measuring circularity remains a major challenge, hindering informed decision-making in the built environment. This study addresses this gap by systematically reviewing existing circularity assessment frameworks for buildings. A systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted following PRISMA guidelines, analyzing 948 records from major databases. The findings reveal gaps in current frameworks, particularly the fragmentation of indicators and an overemphasis on material flows, often neglecting adaptability, repairability, and maintainability. By mapping commonalities between indicator frameworks, data requirements, and aggregation methods, this study contributes to the harmonization of circularity assessment approaches, integrating multi-cycle considerations for buildings and construction products. The results in this research contribute to the development of comprehensive and practical assessment frameworks, facilitating the transition towards a more sustainable and circular built environment.

Keywords: systematic literature review; circularity; indicators; built environment; construction; multi-cycle assessment; assessment framework

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1. Introduction

The transition to a circular economy in the built environment is widely recognized as a key enabler for addressing the construction sector's environmental and resource challenges. The construction sector is one of the largest consumers of energy and raw materials worldwide, and accounts for approximately 42% of total energy consumption, 35% of energy-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and 33% of all materials consumed annually in the EU [1]. Construction and demolition are also responsible for the largest waste stream in Europe by weight. Despite high recycling rates in Europe, more frequently these materials are being downcycled rather than reused in high-value applications, highlighting the urgency of integrating circular economy principles into the sector. The ambition to establish a fully circular European economy by 2050 is strongly reflected in European policies such as the European Green Deal [2] and the Circular Economy Action Plan [3], which set ambitious goals for circular material use by 2050. These policies are implemented through regulatory measures like the EU Taxonomy [4], Construction Product Regulation [5], and Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [6], which emphasize reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting resource efficiency, designing for longevity, and applying circularity principles. However, despite these efforts, there remains a lack of harmonized methodologies and clear, standardized indicators for measuring circularity, which are essential for informed decision-making in the built environment.

The research of Rahla et al. [7] identified vagueness in circular economy definitions, overlap with sustainability, lack of social metrics, and ambiguity in aggregating assessment results as major obstacles to monitoring circularity. Similarly, Kirchherr et al. [8], in their review of 114 definitions, found that most are reductive, missing a systemic integration of environmental, economic, and social dimensions, and often neglecting the R-hierarchy, which prioritizes waste prevention and resource reuse. These hierarchies, ranging from 3Rs to 9Rs, rank circularity strategies from Recovery to Refuse, where Recovery, as the lowest level, is associated with higher environmental impacts and is closest to a linear economy, while Refuse represents the highest level, offering the greatest environmental benefits and circularity potential [9]. More recently, Kirchherr et al. [10] observed an evolution in circular economy definitions, highlighting a shift from incremental efficiency improvements toward systemic transitions, emphasizing sustainability, macro-scale transformations, and supply chain integration. Their refined definition of circular economy highlights the need for a paradigm shift from the 'end of life' to a regenerative economic system, with the aim of promoting value maintenance and sustainable development.

In the present literature review, circularity is defined according to Van Buren et al. [11], as recommended by Kirchherr et al. [8], emphasizing that a circular economy should focus on preserving resources rather than unnecessarily destroying them. This perspective extends beyond waste reduction through recycling to include reducing raw material consumption, designing products for easy disassembly and reuse, prolonging product lifespans through maintenance and repair, integrating recyclables into new products, and recovering raw materials from waste flows. This definition reinforces the importance of retaining the value of materials, components, and buildings through strategies such as reuse, repair, refurbishment, and recycling, aligning with the higher levels of circularity emphasized in the R-hierarchy.

In construction and built environment, the scientometric analysis of circularity indicators in the construction and built environment by Gomis et al. [12] highlights a global surge in research on circularity in the built environment, particularly between 2019 and 2022. Nubholz et al. [13] highlight the absence of a consistent definition of the circular economy (CE) in the building sector, leading to varied interpretations of circular solutions. Çetin et al. [14] categorize these solutions into four key principles: narrowing resource loops by reducing primary resource inputs through efficient production and design; slowing resource loops by designing for durability, adaptability, and reuse to extend product lifespans and minimize unnecessary consumption; closing resource loops by implementing recycling and urban mining practices to retain material value; and regenerating resource loops by prioritizing healthy, renewable resources and supporting environmental regeneration.

Despite the wide range of circularity strategies defined, life cycle assessment (LCA) is a key tool used for evaluating circularity [12], even if it primarily focuses on environmental impacts and does not fully address circular economy principles. LCA's modular approach, from the pre-construction to end-of-life stages, overlooks multiple cycles and fails to incorporate cascading scenarios based on R-strategies, resource loops, life extension, and material reuse which are central to circularity. To address these gaps, scholars such as Eberhardt et al. [15–18] develop a life cycle allocation approach for circular building components that considers multiple life cycles. Meanwhile, Schaubroeck et al. [19] introduce a methodology to assess the cascade potential of in-use construction products, predicting material pathways over time. Instead of focusing on multi-cycling (multiple life cycles of the same product), their approach emphasizes multi-functionality, considering the different uses a product can have throughout its lifespan.

Advancing circular economy principles in the built environment requires robust assessment tools and indicators that capture multi-cycle processes and cascading potential

across building, component, and material scales, while adequately addressing the four core principles of circularity in buildings. Consolidating existing knowledge is crucial for supporting decision-making across the construction life cycle. This study systematically reviews existing circularity assessment frameworks to identify key indicators, data requirements, and aggregation methods, offering a comparative analysis of their strengths, limitations, and applicability. The review is structured in two parts: first, it examines broader thematic trends in circularity assessment across the built environment, and second, it focuses on quantitative indicators and measurement methods at the building scale. By synthesizing the current state of knowledge, the study aims to highlight commonalities, address gaps, and support harmonization efforts to improve circularity assessment approaches. This contributes to the development of comprehensive, user-friendly frameworks that enable the effective measurement of circularity and accelerate the transition toward a circular built environment.

2. Materials and Methods

A systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted to analyze circularity indicators in the built environment. Data were collected on 7 April 2023 from Web of Science, Scopus, Science Direct, and Google Scholar using the search query in all fields (1):

circular* AND building OR construction AND indicator* OR measure* OR assess* (1)

The search identified 20,482 records, with no limitations on year or geographical scope. After removing duplicates, 15,228 records were screened. Following PRISMA guidelines [20] for transparency and replicability, the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1) documented the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion stages, detailing exclusions. The thematic analysis presents results progressively throughout the selection process, offering insights into the trends and topics addressed in circular economy studies in the built environment.

The initial screening of articles was conducted using Rayyan [21], a tool for systematic reviews, which handled automated deduplication and provided a semi-automated screening process to enhance efficiency and reduce selection bias. Rayyan was chosen because it streamlines the initial phases of systematic reviews by enabling blinded inclusion/exclusion screening to minimize bias, while its keyword-based filtering and conflict resolution features facilitate large-scale literature reviews in a time-efficient manner. Publications were included if they focused on circularity in the built environment, proposed or evaluated circularity indicators, and were peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, or reviews. Articles not in English, unrelated to the built environment, or lacking a focus on circularity measurement were excluded.

Thematic analysis of titles, keywords, and abstracts was conducted to identify common themes and trends. VOS Viewer 1.6.19 [22] was then used to visualize the bibliometric networks. The content analysis excludes publications focused on the organizational and urban scales, as the thematic analysis revealed that these account for less than one-third of circularity assessment frameworks. Only quantitative studies measuring circularity were selected for the content analysis, while those focused on life cycle assessment for circularity or comparing allocation approaches and module D scenarios (e.g., [18,23,24]) were excluded. While LCA-based approaches can complement circularity assessments, this study focuses on methodologies that explicitly evaluate circularity indicators, to measure factors such as material retention, adaptability, or reuse potential—key aspects of circular economy strategies, in line with this research objectives.

A total of 64 publications met these criteria, including 4 literature reviews and 12 case studies. In the final stage, the snowball method was applied to integrate technical informa-

tion on circularity assessment methods frequently mentioned in the literature, incorporating other document types such as reports, guidelines, and thesis.

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram and review structure (source: authors).

3. Results of the Thematic Analysis

The following thematic analysis provides an overview of the concept of circularity in the built environment and research trends on its measurement and assessment, spanning from the organizational to the material scale. These findings provide a broader landscape of assessment methods and key themes, supporting the identification of research gaps and opportunities in circularity assessment in the built environment.

3.1. Circularity Is a Blurred Waste-Centric Concept

Life cycle assessment, materials, and construction and demolition waste management are key topics in circular economy studies for the built environment (Figure 2). These often focus on recycling and producing materials using recycled and natural aggregates, mainly in mortars, concrete, and bricks [25,26]. While largely quantitative, these studies measure the performance of building materials in terms of environmental impacts [27], energy [28], and physical–chemical behavior [29], rather than circularity.

Figure 2. Density visualization of authors' keywords (source: authors).

Around 16% of the identified publications are literature reviews on topics such as construction and demolition waste [30], sustainability assessment methods [31], life cycle assessment [32], and material use [33]. Antwi-Afari et al. [34] reviewed 486 bibliometric results on circularity in the construction industry and highlighted significant gaps in circularity research, emphasizing the need for practical approaches and holistic tools that assess performance across the entire lifecycle. They concluded that without these, the circular economy concept struggles to transition from theory to practice. Mrad and Frólén Ribeiro [35], in their review of 87 European studies, found that only 10% focused on construction. They also noted that most research misuses the circular economy term, with few studies addressing actual closed-loop systems, indicating a misunderstanding of the concept's application in construction.

The findings of the present review align with Antwi-Afari et al. [32] and Mrad et al. [33], confirming that circular economy is often used unclearly in the literature, with a strong focus on waste and end-of-life stages. Despite the inclusion of circularity keywords, 68% of the screened publications (n = 948) do not directly address circularity, instead using the term to frame socio-economic and political contexts or to assess environmental impacts in a linear, one-cycle approach.

3.2. LCA Is Used to Measure Circularity

The vast majority of the publications focused on circular economy in the built environment were published with a growing tendency between 2016 and 2023. Analyzing the binary counting of keywords, five main clusters of publications can be identified (Figure 3):

1. Demolition waste (in red);
2. Material Production (in blue);
3. Whole life cycle (in yellow);
4. Building design (in green);
5. Adaptive reuse (in purple).

Figure 3. Network visualization based on binary counting of keywords (source: authors).

However, research is not distributed proportionally across clusters, with production of building materials, and recycling/recyclability accounting for the most significant percentage of the publications.

The first cluster, focusing on demolition waste, accounts for 37.2% of the publications. This includes studies on trends, current practices [36], and life cycle assessments of waste management and CDW recycling [37–39]. Strong ties to construction companies are evident, addressing willingness to pay for CDW [40], business model innovation [41], organizational management [42], and recycling markets [43]. This cluster is closely linked to the third cluster through the use of LCA to assess the life cycle impacts of CDW management [44,45].

The second cluster, focusing on material production, accounts for 27.9% of publications and covers raw material production, including evaluations of environmental sustainability [46], low-carbon construction products [47], product certifications [48], and by-product management [49]. Measurement approaches include dynamic modeling of material stocks and flows [50], material flow analysis [51], and urban metabolism [52] to track and predict regional consumption patterns.

The third cluster, representing 24.7% of publications, focuses on whole life cycle assessments (LCA), from building materials [53] to entire buildings [54]. LCA is used to compare end-of-life scenarios [55], components [56], and supply chains [57]. In 5% of publications, LCA is combined with life cycle costing (LCC) to assess economic costs and benefits [58,59], while less than 1% integrate Social LCA to measure societal impacts [60].

The fourth cluster, focused on building design, comprises 6% of publications. It addresses circular design strategies [17], mainly for new buildings, including design for disassembly [61], adaptability [62], and building-as-service models [63]. BIM plays a crucial role in enabling stakeholder collaboration [64] and facilitating decision-making [65]. It is highlighted for tracing materials and components [66], reducing waste [67], and integrating tools like blockchain [68,69], material passports [70], and circularity measurements [71,72].

The fifth cluster, focused on adaptive reuse, accounts for less than 5% of publications and is linked to the existing building stock [73,74]. It includes theoretical discussions on cultural heritage's role in circularity [75], the digitalization of building stock through GIS and digital twins for life cycle management [76], and circular economy models for heritage landscapes [77]. Emphasizing cultural values and community engagement [78,79], it relates to city-scale circularity. Keywords like "criteria" and "indicators" in this cluster often refer to evaluation frameworks, with the Level(s) framework commonly used to improve circularity [80,81].

LCA is the most commonly used methodology ($n = 645$) for assessing circularity in the built environment, but it faces challenges in accounting for reuse possibilities and applicability during the design stage [34]. Limitations of methodologies like cradle-to-cradle and LCA include data availability, accuracy, and comparability issues related to different system boundaries, units, and sources used for environmental impact data [13,82]. Although LCA is widely accepted for environmental impact assessment, it is often applied from a linear perspective, lacking a consistent multi-cycle approach for circularity [23,83,84]. These results emphasize the need for complementary indicators to improve transparency and decision-making.

3.3. Circularity Assessment Addresses Mostly Reuse of Building Components

The analysis of results focused on indicators to measure circularity ($n = 253$) confirms the rising interest in the topic of circularity assessment in the building sector, with most of the publications concentrated after 2020 (Figure 4). The top 10 countries represent 66% of publications, with Italy, Belgium, and the United Kingdom as the countries with most publications on the topic.

Figure 4. Distribution of publications per year (source: authors).

Most publications (76.7%) focus on a single scale. Of these, 33.5% address the whole building scale, 17% focus on building materials, and 23% on components or elements. Less than 20% explore circularity at the urban and regional scale [85,86], and only 9% focus on organizational indicators [87,88].

At the building scale, most publications focus on the design stage, emphasizing BIM parametric tools [89–91] and decision-making support [92–94]. Common circularity strategies include adaptive reuse [95,96], design for disassembly [97] and reversibility [98,99]. Fewer publications address adaptability [100,101] or maintainability's role in circularity [102]. Though these strategies target whole buildings, they often focus on deconstruction, component harvesting, and reuse of components and materials [103].

“Component” and “element” are often used interchangeably and considered synonymous. Commonly studied elements include internal walls [104], façade systems [105], and structural elements [106,107]. Buyle et al. [104,108] use LCA and LCC assessments to compare demountable and reusable internal wall alternatives. Van Gulck et al. [105] developed methods to assess circularity in façade systems at the early design stage, and later to integrate multi-cycling into life cycle assessments [24]. Androsevic et al. [109] and Lam et al. [110] focus on semi-quantified circularity indicators based on connection types to determine reuse potential, emphasizing reversibility and ease of disassembly.

At the material scale, construction and demolition waste (CDW) and end-of-life management are key topics, focusing on recycling and recyclability. Tseng et al. [111] conduct a cost–benefit analysis of CDW recycling, while Di Maria et al. [112] compare downcycling and recycling scenarios using LCA and LCC to integrate environmental and economic assessments. Studies also focus on composite materials with recycled content [113]. Concrete and cement are commonly examined [114], while fewer publications address timber [115] or earth construction [116], for instance.

Fifty-nine publications adopt a multi-scale approach. A common link between the urban and material scales involves material stock assessments and urban mining potential [117–119]. The building and organizational scales often focus on stakeholder collaboration [92,120] or business models [121,122]. At the component level, research frequently examines material choices, such as the reuse of metal waste in facades [123] or the circularity of timber walls [124].

4. Results of the Content Analysis

4.1. Mapping Quantitative Circularity Assessment Frameworks

The present review identifies four key review studies on quantitative circularity assessment frameworks, published between 2020 and 2022. Despite employing systematic methodologies, each study addresses distinct research questions (Table 1). Khadim et al. [125] focus on standardizing circularity measurement frameworks, offering an overview of key frameworks up to 2021. Zhang et al. [126] propose a Building Circularity assessment that integrates a material flow model, material passport, and circularity calculation. Cambier et al. [127] examine tools supporting circular building during the design stage, aligning them with stakeholder priorities. Askar et al. [128] review the role of design adaptability, analyzing categories, criteria, and weighting methods in current frameworks.

Across the four reviews, 87 circularity support tools were identified. Despite similar search queries and timeframes, the results differ due to the specific research focus of each study. Askar et al. [128] include indicators for building adaptability, while Cambier et al. [127] consider tools beyond indicators, such as design guidelines and reuse marketplaces. Khadim et al. [125] concentrate on indicator frameworks for the built environment, and Zhang et al. [126] incorporate LCA-based methodologies and multi-sector frameworks.

Table 1. Literature reviews on circularity measuring frameworks and tools (source: authors).

Author	Aim	Outcome	Time Frame
[127]	Compare the functionalities of available tools with the needs identified by designers	Classification of existing tools according to design phase and design need	Before 2020
[126]	Develop a CE assessment method for architecture, engineering, and construction	Building Circularity assessment framework including material flow, material passport, and circularity calculation	Before 2021
[125]	Standardize existing measurement frameworks	Identification of key circularity assessment tools and derivative works	2015–2021
[128]	Integrate adaptability in circularity assessment frameworks	Framework of circularity requirements at multiple scales	Before 2022

Forty-one frameworks met the criteria of this review, focusing on quantitative frameworks for measuring circularity from material to whole-building scale, as shown in Table 2. Several frameworks were cited in three or more reviews, including the Building Circularity Indicator [129], Material Circularity Indicator [130], MAD-CI [131], Platform CB’23 Core method [132], Circularity Calculator [133], and the Circular Building Assessment Prototype [134]. MCI and BCI have the most derivative frameworks, such as the Building Circularity Indicator—Disassembly reconsidered [135] or the MCI—Probabilistic Circular Economy Index [136]. For other frequently mentioned frameworks, such as Platform CB23, Circularity Calculator, and the Circular Building Assessment Prototype, detailed information on indicators and data is scarcely reported in the reviewed literature.

Twelve case studies published between 2019 and 2023 tested the application of assessment frameworks in various contexts, such as products and BIM applications, without developing new frameworks. These studies confirm the BCI and MCI as the most recognized circularity frameworks internationally [109,113,137–145].

The present review identified 32 additional publications developing quantitative circularity indicators for buildings, also included in Table 2. These studies often contribute to theoretical research in areas such as resilience [146], flexibility scenarios [147], urban mining feasibility [118], and the integration of social aspects [148]. Their absence from recent reviews and case studies suggests these frameworks are still in early development and not yet widely influential. While they are not further analyzed in this paper, future research should integrate these emerging insights.

Table 2. Quantitative circularity assessment frameworks identified (source: authors).

Scale	Framework	Prev.	Crev.	Ref.
Multiple	3DR Method to Quantify Circularity in Buildings		x	[146]
	Circular Construction Site		x	[149]
	Circular Economy Engagement Tool (Regenerate)		x	[150]
	Circular Economy Potential Index		x	[151]
	Circular Transition Indicators	x		[152]
	Circularity Calculator	x		[133]
	Material Recovery potential index	x	x	[153]
	MCI Circular Construction Indicator		x	[154]
	MCI Methodology to Assess Circularity in Building Construction		x	[148]
Urban Mining Feasibility Method		x	[118]	
Building	ABD Adaptable Building Design	x		[155]
	ARP Adaptive Reuse Potential Model	x		[156]
	AdaptSTAR Model	x		[157]
	ARCH Circular Environmental Indicator Framework		x	[158]
	BCI—Disassembly Reconsidered	x		[135]
	BCI Alba Concepts	x		[159]
	BCI Building Circularity Indicator	x		[129]
BCI Predictive Building Circularity Model	x	x	[160]	

Table 2. Cont.

Scale	Framework	Prev.	Crev.	Ref.
	BIM-based Building Circularity Assessment	x		[161]
	BIM-based Functional Flexibility Assessment		x	[91]
	Building Research Establishment's Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM)	x		[162]
	Carbon Footprint and Design for Disassembly Metrics		x	[163]
	C-CALC	x		[164]
	CE Meter	x		[165]
	Circular Building Assessment Prototype	x		[134]
	Circular Construction Evaluation Framework	x	x	[166]
	Circularity Degree in Existing Buildings		x	[167]
	Core Measuring Method	x		[132]
	Design Criteria for Circular Buildings	x	x	[168]
	FLEX	x	x	[100]
	Framework for Circular Buildings	x		[169]
	Green Maintainability Indicators		x	[102]
	GRO	x		[170]
	IconCUR	x		[171]
	Integrated Energy Performance and Circularity	x		[172]
	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design—Materials and Resources (LEED)	x		[173]
	Level(s)	x		[174]
	MCI MADASTER Circularity Indicator (MAD-CI)	x		[131]
	MCI Probabilistic Circular Economy Index		x	[136]
	Preliminary Assessment Adaptation Model	x		[175]
	RIPAT 1.0	x		[176]
	Spatial Assessment of Generality and Adaptability (SAGA)	x		[177]
	Synthetic Economic Environmental Indicator	x	x	[178]
	BCI Modified Alba Concept (for Foundations)	x		[179]
	BCI Modified Building circularity indicator	x	x	[58]
	BIM-Based Whole-Life Performance Estimator	x	x	[89]
	Circular Assessment Criteria for Envelope	x	x	[180]
	Circular assessment Method for Façade Renovation		x	[105]
	Circular Economy Index	x		[181]
	Deconstructability Assessment Method		x	[182]
	Design for Reuse and Recycling Calculator BBRI-VCB	x		[183]
	Disassembly and Deconstruction Analytics System D-DAS	x	x	[89]
	Economic and Technical Reusability Predictor		x	[107,184]
	Express Methodology for the Assessment of Circularity Level		x	[185]
	Indicators for Recovery Opportunities in Material Passports		x	[186]
	Linking LCA and Detachability Assessment		x	[110]
	Linking LCA and Reusability Assessment		x	[187]
	MCI Material Circularity Indicator for Construction	x	x	[59]
	Predictive Building Systemic Circularity Model	x	x	[93]
	Resource Duration Indicator	x		[188]
	Sequential Disassembly Planning for Buildings		x	[74]
	Sustainability of Architectural Reclamation		x	[103]
	Sustainable Circular System Design		x	[189]
	CE-Based 10 R Evaluation Framework for Material Selection		x	[190]
	Gypsum End-of-Life Measurement Indicator GEOLMI	x	x	[191]
	Material Reutilization Score	x		[192]
	MCI Material Circularity Indicator	x		[130]
	Modeling the Optimal Chain of Products for Specific Material Circularity		x	[193]
	Potential for Material Circulation		x	[147]
	Recyclability Assessment in the Design Stage		x	[115]

Prev: previous reviews. Crev: current review.

4.2. Most Commonly Used Circularity Assessment Frameworks

The analysis of overlapping reviews allows for the identification of the most frequently referenced and influential methodologies in the field. Table 3 provides a comparative summary, outlining their evaluation processes, key indicators, and application maturity.

Table 3. Summary of the most influential circularity assessment frameworks (source: authors).

Framework	Evaluation Process	Key Indicators	Application Maturity
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	Designed to measure the circularity of material flows within products, considering both technical and biological cycles.	Material flows, lifespan, usage utility	Widely applicable across industries but not specifically tailored to construction.
Madaster Circularity Indicator (MAD-CI)	Material passports and reuse potential of building components.	Material flows, reusability, residual material value.	Commercially available; primarily used in the Netherlands.
Building Circularity Indicator (BCI)	Adapts Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) buildings, integrating disassembly potential and life cycle stages.	Material flows, material reuse potential, disassembly scores.	Commercially available; primarily used in the Netherlands.
Platform CB'23 Core Method	Multi-scale assessment method from material to building-level circularity.	Existing material stock, environmental impact, material value retention.	Theoretical framework; currently lacks practical implementation tools.
Level(s) Framework	Qualitative and quantitative indicators to assess sustainability at the building level.	Bills of quantities, waste generation, adaptability, deconstruction.	Promoted by the EU; voluntary reporting framework applicable to residential and office buildings.
Circularity Calculator	Decision-tree approach to assess reuse, refurbishment, and recycling scenarios.	Circularity score, value capture, recycled content.	Prototype developed in a research project; not specific to the construction industry.
Circular Building Assessment Prototype (CBAP)—BAMB Project	Semi-automated tool using BIM data to calculate reuse potential.	Resource productivity, reuse potential, and alignment with Reversible Building Design strategies.	Prototype developed in a research project; not publically available as a functional tool

The Material Circularity Indicator (MCI), developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation [130], assesses the circularity of materials and products but is not specifically tailored to construction. While applicable at the building scale, it requires complementary methods to account for building elements and design aspects like disassembly and adaptability [128]. A key strength is its consideration of both technical and biological cycles [126]. However, it excludes material losses during extraction and manufacturing, overlooks quality degradation in salvaged materials, and does not account for the economic cycle or material recovery based on connection types [125,126]. Derivatives like Jiang et al.'s MCI [59] address some gaps by integrating residual value and linking MCI with design for disassembly, though this increases data complexity [121]. Madaster's Circularity Indicator (MAD-CI) further builds on the MCI, centralizing building stock data for reuse with material passports [131].

The Building Circularity Indicator (BCI) is discussed in the reviews by Khadim et al. [121], Askar et al. [124], and Cambier et al. [123], with the latter focusing on the version of Alba Concepts [159]. Developed originally by Verbene [129], the BCI extends the MCI framework to the building scale using Brand's shearing layers [194], incorporating design for disassembly based on Durmisevic's Disassembly Determining factors [195]. However, Khadim et al. [121] identify some limitations, for instance, its mass-dependent calculations—which create a bias toward heavier materials, the highly subjective disassembly assessments, and the exclusion of materials used during operation and maintenance. Several derivative works address these limitations. Cottafava and Ritzen [160] introduce embodied energy and carbon as normalizing factors instead of mass. Van Vliet [135] refines the disassembly assessment with a detailed weighting system for connections, and Braakman et al. [58] incorporate maintenance repairs and recycling efficiency. The latest version of the BCI [196] integrates an environmental cost indicator as a normalizing factor, addressing the main limitation identified by Khadim et al. [121] by reducing the bias towards heavier materials and aligning the results more closely with environmental impacts.

Level(s) is a European framework providing a common language for assessing sustainability across a building's lifecycle [174]. It focuses on six macro-objectives, with Macro-objective 2 addressing circular material lifecycles through four indicators: bills of

quantities, construction and demolition waste, adaptability, and deconstruction. While the first two are quantitative, the latter rely on qualitative checklists. Though Level(s) promotes harmonized methodologies, its data requirements are often misaligned with current practices, making the process time-consuming and subjective. Askar et al. [124] also highlight the lack of a clear adaptability assessment method, with the framework relying on external tools that may not align with its objectives.

The Platform CB'23 core measurement method [132] is frequently cited in the literature. Though not an assessment tool itself, it provides a methodological framework for assessing circularity at multiple scales, including material, product, structure, and area [122]. The method uses three key indicators: existing material stock, environmental assessment, and material value retention [121]. It also incorporates socio-economic and technical factors such as quality degradation, adaptive capacity, and material availability. A key limitation is the lack of an aggregated circularity, not providing a clear basis for comparability and decision-making.

The Circularity Calculator [133], while not specifically tailored to construction, serves as an online decision tree tool that calculates a circularity score from a bill of materials [121]. Users input data such as product mass, material costs, and percentages of recycled or reused content. These data are then processed to generate scores across four indicators: circularity, value capture, recycled content, and reuse index. The tool allows for the comparison of various circularity scenarios—reuse, refurbishment, remanufacture, and recycling—helping users make informed design choices to improve product sustainability [124].

The Circular Building Assessment Prototype (CBAP) is a semi-automated tool developed within the BAMB project that uses BIM data on an online platform, allowing users to upload files from common 3D modeling software [134]. The CBAP calculates reuse potential by considering material selection, design parameters, and the building's lifecycle [121]. It supports decision-making by assessing resource productivity and reuse potential for both new and existing buildings and is linked to Reversible Building Design strategies [130]. However, CBAP remains a prototype and is not accessible to circular economy practitioners [124].

4.3. Data Requirements to Measure Circularity

The studies reviewed provide an overview of circularity assessment frameworks, but as noted by Khadim et al. [121], indicators are scattered across multiple frameworks and lack practitioner confidence. Existing reviews focus on strategies but do not systematically identify the data needed for assessment. This section maps the data requirements of key circularity frameworks, examining their relationship with scales and R-levels.

The results indicate that despite the diversity of frameworks, there are redundancies and overlaps, and only a limited number of data requirements (30) were identified. Table 4 presents a selection of common circularity indicators, streamlining redundancies such as different units (mass vs. percentage), and the breakdown of indicators (e.g., ease of reuse instead of detachability and connection accessibility).

Most indicators focus on closing resource loops (37.5%) through recycling and slowing loops (40.6%) by keeping resources in use via reuse. Narrowing loops, related to efficiency improvements (12.5%), reduces virgin material use, water, and energy demand, while regenerating (6.5%) involves avoiding toxic materials and promoting renewable resources. Most indicators target material efficiency by reducing raw material consumption through bio-based and secondary materials. Less than a third (29%) address current circularity, focusing on secondary materials at the design stage, while about 70% focus on future circularity, such as reuse or recycling at end-of-life. Indicators for disassembly rank second, while adaptive reuse, adaptability, repairability, and maintainability are rarely covered.

Table 4. Key data requirements identified (source: authors).

Scale	Data Requirements	R-Level	Circular Principles
Building	Spatio-functional adaptive capacity	Rethink	Slow
Building and component	Energy use	Reduce	Narrow
	Water use	Reduce	Narrow
	Economic value loss	-	Close
	Financial residual value	-	Close
	Intensity of use	Rethink	Slow
Component	Ease of recovery (harvesting)	Reuse–Recycle	Slow
	Detachability of connection type	Reuse–Recycle	Slow
	Accessibility of connection	Reuse–Recycle	Slow
	Amount of actual refurbished after use	Refurbish	Slow
	Amount of actual remanufactured after use	Remanufacture	Slow
	Length of use phase	-	Slow
	Number of maintenance cycles	Repair	Slow
	Techno-functional quality	Repair	Slow
Component and material	Amount of secondary materials from reuse	Reuse	Slow
	Amount of materials viable for reuse	Reuse	Slow
	Environmental impact according to LCA	Reduce	(all)
Material	Mass of virgin material	Reduce	Narrow
	Amount of scarce materials	Reduce	Narrow
	Amount of toxic materials	Refuse	Regenerate
	Amount of renewable primary materials	-	Narrow
	Amount of secondary materials used	Reuse–Recycle	Close
	Amount of recycled input	Recycle	Close
	Amount of materials viable for secondary used	Reuse–Recycle	Close
	Amount actually collected after use	Reuse–Recycle	Close
	Amount of materials viable for recycling	Recycle	Close
	Ease of recycling	Recycle	Close
	Amount of waste stream downcycled	Recycle-Recovery	Close
	Amount of materials used for energy recovery	Recovery	Close
	Amount of unrecoverable waste	Reduce	Narrow

Material is the most assessed scale, but the distinction between material and component scales is often unclear. While virgin material mass refers to raw materials, indicators like reused material percentages often refer to transformed products, which should be considered at the component scale. This distinction affects the interpretation of R-levels and life cycle cascading. Reuse, by definition, applies to products in their original function, while repurposing or remanufacturing involves higher transformation and resource use. Most frameworks fail to differentiate between R-levels, often aggregating them under “secondary materials”, despite potentially significant differences in environmental impacts.

4.4. Aggregation and Scoring Approaches

Although circularity data requirements share common ground across frameworks, the methods for combining these requirements into a single score vary significantly. The goal of single scores is to provide a holistic, comparable view of a building’s circularity to support decision-making. Aggregation typically involves weighting components based on environmental impact, disassembly potential, and material origin, though not all methodologies consider these factors, and the way they are quantified also differs. Most frameworks begin with a Linear Flow Index (LFI) or a similar indicator to measure the linearity of material flows (Table 5).

Table 5. Summary of factors considered in the aggregation of scores (source: authors).

Framework	Material Flow	Utility	Disassembly	Environmental Impact	Economic Value	Other
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	LFI—Virgin materials and unrecoverable waste	Adjust for lifespan and usage utility	Not included	Not included	No direct consideration	Risk indicators, environmental impact indicators, and profitability indicators.
Madaster Circularity Indicator (CI)	LFI—Virgin materials and unrecoverable waste	Adjusts for lifespan only	Qualitative design for disassembly criteria in the EOL phase	Not included	No direct consideration	Construction, use, and end-of-life phases; data quality correction factor
Building Circularity Indicator (BCI)	LFI—Virgin materials and unrecoverable waste	Adjusts for lifespan only	Adjusts for quantitative disassembly score	Environmental Impact Cost Factor included in final score	No direct consideration	-
Circularity Calculator	Virgin materials, wasted, downcycled, and scrap materials	Not included	Not included	Not included	Value Capture Indicator	Cycled Content Indicator; Reuse Index

The Material Circularity Indicator (MCI), Madaster Circularity Indicator (CI), and Building Circularity Indicator (BCI) all rely on the LFI to measure the linearity of material flows, which accounts for the proportion of virgin materials and unrecoverable waste in a product’s lifecycle. However, the LFI is calculated and used differently across these frameworks. The MCI adjusts the LFI with a Utility Factor, which considers both the product’s lifespan and usage intensity compared to industry averages. This ensures that products with longer lifespans and more intensive use are rewarded with higher circularity scores, even if their material inputs are not entirely circular. The final MCI score, ranging from 0 to 1, reflects a balance between material efficiency and product longevity [124].

Similarly, the Mad-CI applies a Utility Factor ($F(X)$), but this primarily adjusts for product lifespan rather than usage intensity. This means that while Mad-CI rewards longer-lasting products, it does not account for how intensively the product is used. In Mad-CI, the LFI and Utility Factor work together to produce an overall circularity score, ranging from 0% (fully linear) to 100% (fully circular). Unlike the MCI, the Mad-CI includes a data quality correction factor, which ensures that the overall score reflects the quality and completeness of the input data. The Mad-CI also calculates separate circularity scores for the construction, use, and end-of-life phases [125]. In the construction phase, it assesses the origin of materials (reused, recycled, and renewable), aggregating the percentage of the total material mass, though all material types are treated equally despite differing environmental impacts (e.g., reuse and recycling are considered equivalent). During the use phase, the product’s functional lifespan is compared to industry averages (L/L_{avg}), expressed in years. In the end-of-life phase, the score considers the percentage of materials that can be reused or recycled, factoring in recycling efficiency, and reusability is assessed qualitatively using design for disassembly criteria. These scores are complementary indicators that provide specific insights at different stages of a building’s lifecycle but are not directly aggregated in the overall circularity score.

The BCI method uses a hierarchical approach to measure circularity, starting at the material level and gradually aggregating results at the product, element, and building levels [196]. It follows a similar approach, starting from the LFI, but places more emphasis on disassembly potential by integrating a disassembly score alongside the LFI. This score evaluates how easily materials can be disassembled for reuse or recycling, assigning values based on connection types, accessibility, and intersections. The latest version of BCI also incorporates an Environmental Impact Cost Factor, which weights materials

or components by their environmental impacts, converting LCA results into monetary values [196]. This ensures that materials with higher environmental costs contribute more to the final score. This integration of disassembly potential and environmental cost makes the BCI particularly well suited for assessing not only material flows but also the ease of recovery and environmental impact at the end of the lifecycle.

Differently, the Circularity Calculator introduces a broader approach by focusing on both material flows and economic value retention [133,196]. Its Circularity Indicator operates similarly to the LFI but offers a more detailed view by distinguishing between downcycled materials (which are recycled into lower-value uses) and scrapped materials (which are lost entirely). This results in a more nuanced assessment of material flow degradation compared to the LFI, which aggregates all recycled and reused materials without considering their quality. Additionally, the Circularity Calculator includes several complementary indicators, such as the Value Capture Indicator, which measures the retained economic value of materials through circular strategies like reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling. Although the Value Capture Indicator does not contribute to the overall circularity score, it provides useful insights into the financial benefits of circular practices. Other indicators in the Circularity Calculator include the Cycled Content Indicator, which evaluates the percentage of recycled or renewable materials in the product, and the Reuse Index, which measures the product's potential for lifecycle extension based on its number of reuse cycles.

The analysis of the aggregation approaches of circularity frameworks reveals key distinctions in how material flows, utility, disassembly potential, and economic value are integrated. The MCI, CI, and BCI use the LFI to assess material flow linearity, and the Circularity Calculator's Circularity Indicator offers a more nuanced understanding by distinguishing between downcycled and scrapped materials. However, while the Circularity Calculator acknowledges the difference between these two categories conceptually, it does not reflect this distinction in the calculation itself, as the formula does not assign different weights or penalties to these categories. The Utility Factor plays a critical role in both the MCI and Madaster CI, with the MCI accounting for both lifespan and usage intensity, making it more responsive to usage patterns, whereas the Madaster CI focuses solely on lifespan, emphasizing product longevity. Additionally, the Madaster CI's phase-specific scoring for construction, use, and end-of-life phases contrasts with the BCI, which integrates disassembly potential and a hierarchical approach focused on product scales (from building to the material). The BCI is the only method that incorporates both disassembly scores and environmental impact, which are less emphasized in other frameworks. Finally, the Circularity Calculator stands out for incorporating economic value into its assessment through the Value Capture Indicator, providing complementary information on economic factors.

5. Discussion

The results of this review reveal the main frameworks and highlight a growing research trend. By systematically mapping the most used indicators (Table 4) and the methods used for their quantification (Table 5), this study contributes to harmonizing circularity measurement approaches and consolidates current knowledge. Building on previous reviews, such as the scientometric analysis by Gomis [12], which identifies broad themes in circularity assessment, this study directly addresses the need for a systematized list of indicators and data requirements. Similarly, Khadim's [121] comprehensive review provides an essential foundation by categorizing key frameworks and indicator types, but this study expands on those findings by comparing data input requirements and aggregation methods—crucial steps toward a harmonized methodology. Despite the vast quantity of frameworks identified (Table 2), many remain confined to academic discussions,

lacking widespread practical adoption in the industry. This underscores the need for further development and real-world validation to bridge the gap between research and industry application and ensure these tools can effectively support decision-making in practice.

One key issue identified is the lack of a systematic approach to data collection and assessment across circularity methods. Khadim et al. [121] highlight considerable variability in indicators, data, units, and scoring methods, making comparisons difficult. However, this research shows that many methodologies rely on a similar set of data requirements, highlighting the potential to establish standardized assessment criteria that enhance consistency and comparability across studies. Developing such standards could improve integration into policy instruments and facilitate industry-wide adoption.

Another significant gap in existing methods is their heavy reliance on material flow analysis, typically quantified in mass, and disassembly at the product/component level, while neglecting crucial aspects of circularity such as adaptability, repairability, and maintainability [62,130]. This study reinforces the limitations of this approach by demonstrating that many frameworks project future circularity based on idealized scenarios, rather than assessing current circularity achieved in practice, such as adaptive reuse. This confirms the findings of Nußholz et al. [13], which indicate a research gap in academic literature focusing the reuse of materials and components of existing buildings. To address this, future frameworks should adopt a lifecycle perspective that quantifies circularity across multiple cycles and considering the interconnection of circularity strategies, rather than relying on one or two-cycle projections.

Harmonizing calculation methods for circularity is essential. Existing designs for disassembly and deconstruction scores are not comparable across frameworks. For instance, the Level(s) circularity score is based on the “best possible outcome” defined by the user (reuse, recycle, landfill). Durmisevic’s [195] methodology, frequently cited, includes several indicators, but studies often apply it only partially, focusing mainly on connection types and accessibility neglecting morphology, geometry, and assembly sequences. Moreover, although it provides a numeric score, the method still depends on subjective assessments. This underscores the challenge of developing frameworks that are both flexible and comprehensive enough to ensure accuracy.

The Mad-CI [131] offers a macro-level view of material circularity across a building’s lifecycle, while the Disassembly Metric provides micro-level insights into component reuse. Together, they offer a more complete understanding of building circularity. The BCI method combines the Linear Flow Index, disassembly score, and environmental impact factors, making it one of the most comprehensive methodologies. Despite that, this review identifies that the BCI does not account for aspects like the Utility Factor (Madaster), value retention (Platform CB’23), or differentiation of the R-hierarchy (Circularity Calculator), limiting its applicability for a multi-cycle approach.

The literature review shows that most frameworks neglect multiple lifecycles and the integration of an R-hierarchy, which risks undermining the circular economy concept and limiting its benefits [8]. This is a critical gap, as extending the life of building components through R-strategies—reuse, repair, refurbishment, and remanufacturing—is central to circularity [11]; yet, it remains underrepresented in measurement frameworks. Incorporating multi-cycle considerations into circularity assessments would allow for a better understanding of the long-term value and environmental benefits of materials, potentially through cascading scenarios across the lifecycle [19]. This approach prioritizes higher-value strategies, such as reuse and repair, over lower-value ones like recycling. Among the tools analyzed, only the Circularity Calculator [133,197] separately collects data for recycled, reused, refurbished, or remanufactured materials by mass, and Zhang et al. [122] propose

factoring the R-hierarchy into assessments, though without detailing how these factors can be measured.

While input data often overlaps across methodologies, the greatest variability lies in how scores are aggregated and weighted. Platform CB'23 [132] highlights this challenge, emphasizing the need for a clear, agreed-upon method for weighting indicators. However, different projects and stakeholders prioritize various aspects of circularity, making a one-size-fits-all approach difficult to implement in practice. Kirchherr et al. [10] underscore the systemic shift required for circularity, enabled by collaboration between key stakeholders, including industry, policymakers, consumers, and academia. This perspective reinforces the need for circularity assessment frameworks to support decision-making across the entire value chain, where stakeholders with divergent priorities must be reconciled. Factors such as economic feasibility, technical quality, and spatial adaptability play an important role for different stakeholders yet the present review shows that those are still far from being widely adopted. If circularity frameworks are to influence practice, they must curate and balance these values, ensuring that assessment methods are adaptable to different project needs and life cycle stages, while maintaining methodological consistency. Future research should prioritize the validation of identified data requirements against key policy frameworks and legal requirements, such as the Level(s) framework [174]. Aligning future circularity assessment tools with the regulatory developments proposed by the Circular Economy Action Plan [3] and the Construction Product Regulation [5], will enhance their applicability and support compliance with upcoming legislation.

Digitalization plays a crucial role in optimizing data management and streamlining circularity assessments [14]. Emerging technologies such as BIM and material passports [70,186] can enhance data traceability across multiple cycles. Material passports offer a promising solution by providing detailed information on the composition, origin, and reuse potential of building materials, ensuring traceability for end-of-life scenarios. Their integration could significantly improve the accuracy of circularity assessments and enhance communication between stakeholders, fostering informed decision-making and supporting business models such as Building-as-a-Service or buy-back schemes [63,121,122]. Further research is needed to determine what data are already being collected, how it is stored, and where critical gaps remain, ensuring that these tools can be leveraged effectively to capture, store, and update circularity-related data over multiple life cycles. This will make the application of future frameworks more time-efficient and attractive for stakeholders, supporting the effective implementation of circularity assessments.

Finally, while life cycle assessment (LCA) remains the most widely accepted method for quantifying environmental impacts, it does not inherently assess circularity. The data requirements identified in this study could strengthen end-of-use scenario modeling by supporting the development of a cascading database for building elements and components, as suggested by Schaubroeck [19], thereby facilitating the transition from linear modular approaches to multi-cycle LCA. This would allow LCA methodologies to better integrate circularity principles while maintaining their accuracy in environmental impact quantification.

6. Conclusions

This research identifies critical gaps and opportunities in the existing literature on circularity assessment in the built environment. It highlights the need for a more systematic and standardized approach to data collection and assessment, focusing on a holistic view of circularity that includes adaptive reuse, spatial adaptability, repairability, and maintainability. Rather than proposing a new framework, this study advances the harmonization of existing quantitative indicators and assessment methodologies for buildings. The structured comparison of key indicators and aggregation methods facilitates a clearer

understanding of gaps and overlaps in current approaches, supporting more consistent and reliable circularity assessments in future research and practice. In the future, incorporating multi-cycle considerations with emerging technologies like BIM and material passports can enhance the effectiveness and applicability of circularity assessments. Engaging a broad range of stakeholders is essential to developing user-friendly tools that meet industry needs in different contexts and life cycle stages. Addressing these requirements can contribute to more robust, comprehensive, and user-friendly circularity assessment frameworks, driving the transition towards a sustainable and circular built environment.

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